

Voltammetric Studies on some Arylhydrazones of α -Cyanoketones and α -Cyanooesters

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The redox characteristics of the title compounds have been studied using DC, cyclic voltammetry and coulometry in benzonitrile at RDE. These compounds are oxidised in one-electron transfer process followed by deprotonation leading to dimerisation. The reduction process differs according to the nature of the compound and the electron-withdrawing power of the substituent in the α -position. They can be reduced in a single two electron or two one-electron waves leading in both the cases to saturation of the hydrazone moiety.

In previous investigation¹, it has been shown that arylhydrazonomesoxalonitriles (1) are electrochemically active in proton-free benzonitrile. These compounds are oxidised in a single irreversible one-electron transfer process forming the corresponding radical cation which undergoes dimerisation reaction. The electrochemical reduction occurs through acceptance of two electrons in two successive irreversible one-electron waves following the well known ECEC-mechanism. In connection with this work we report here the redox characteristics of different substituted ethyl α -cyanoarylhydrazono-glyoxalates (2) and arylhydrazono-3-keto-3-phenylpropionitriles (3).

a, X=H, b, X=NO₂, c, X=Br, d, X=Cl, e, X=CH₃,
f, X=OCH₃, g, X=NH₂, h, X=H (N-CH₃)

Experimental

All compounds were prepared following the reported procedures². The compounds were crystallised from ethanol and the purity was checked by tlc. The structures of compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral data.

Benzonitrile (BN; Rotitainerm) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure from orthophosphoric acid, followed by repeated distillation from phosphorus pentoxide and fractional distillation from

potassium metal. The supporting electrolyte tetra-n-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP; Fluka-Swiss) was crystallised from ethanol-water (9:1, v/v) mixture and dried under reduced pressure.

The voltammetric measurements were carried out using a VSG 72 potential scan generator, a PCA 72C (Bank Electronic) potential control amplifier, a Servoger XY (Metra-watt) recorder, a T 2201 (Hartman & Braun) digital multimeter and a coulometer (Bank Electronic). The rotating platinum disc electrode (RDE) was mounted to a Metrohm (750 rpm) rotating motor.

The electrochemical measurements were carried out in dry benzonitrile (BN) containing 0.1 M tetra-n-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as supporting electrolyte. The voltammetric study involved direct current (DC) voltammetry at a rotating platinum disc electrode (RDE) and cyclic voltammetry at a stationary platinum disc electrode. The number of electrons participating in each electrode process was obtained by the controlled potential coulometry (CPC) at platinum sheet electrode. The electrode potentials were measured against saturated Ag/AgCl/Cl⁻ (BN) electrode, which was from time to time calibrated against the redox potential of cobaltocinium/cobaltocene system³. The standard potential of Ag/AgCl/Cl⁻ (BN) electrode against the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) was -176 mV⁴.

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE): Electrolysis of ethyl α -cyano- α -p-chlorophenylhydrazono-glyoxalate (2d; 300 mg) was carried out twice both in acetonitrile and benzonitrile. The potential was adjusted at a value on the limiting current plateau (+2.2 V at oxidation and -1.2 V at reduction).

The electrolysis was stopped after the passage of a quantity of electricity corresponding to the uptake of 1 mole of electron per mole of the product for oxidation and 2 moles for reduction. In each case, after electrolysis, the resulting solution was evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was extracted with ethyl acetate which was evaporated in turn. The resulting mixture was chromatographed on thin layer silica gel plates using chloroform as solvent.

Reduction product of CPE: A quantitative yield of the original compound **2d** was obtained (Found: C, 52.33; H, 3.84; Cl, 13.98; N, 16.80. Calcd. for: C, 52.49; H, 3.98; Cl, 14.12; N, 16.70%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 220 (NH), 2 220 (CN), 1 760 (ester CO) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 1.4 (3H, t, CH_3CH_2), 3.6 (2H, q, CH_3CH_2), 7.2–7.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 10.0 (1H, s br, NH).

Oxidation products of CPE: Two main products were obtained. (i) The zone with R_f value 0.68 was scrapped off the plate and extracted with acetonitrile, filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure. The resulting solid (55%) was identified as compound **4** (Found: C, 41.20; H, 3.01; Cl, 22.40; N, 13.12. Calcd. for: C, 41.38; H, 3.13; Cl, 22.26; N, 13.17%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 220–3 300 (two NH), 2 220 (CN), 1 760, 1 750 (ester CO), 1 630 (C=N) and 1 220 cm^{-1} (ClO_4^-); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 1.4 (6H, t, $2 \times \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2$), 3.6 (4H, q, $2 \times \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2$), 7.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.0 (2H, s br, $2 \times \text{NH}$). (ii) The zone with R_f value 0.79 was scrapped and extracted as above to yield the product (30%) which was identified as compound **5** (Found: C, 52.52; H, 3.53; Cl, 14.23; N, 16.59. Calcd. for: C, 25.69; H, 3.59; Cl, 14.17; N, 16.77%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 200–3 300 (two NH), 2 220 (CN), 1 760–1 750 (ester CO) and 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 1.4 (6H, t, $2 \times \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2$), 3.6 (4H, q, $2 \times \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2$), 7.2–7.4 (6H, m, ArH) and 10.0 (2H, s br, $2 \times \text{NH}$).

Results and Discussion

The voltammetric redox data of the compounds (2a–h and 3a–h) are summarised in Table 1. Figs. 1 and 2 represent typical DC and cyclic voltammograms of the compounds respectively.

Ethyl arylhydrazonoglyoxalate (2a–h): All the compounds behave similarly in shape in both oxidation and reduction. They are oxidised in a single irreversible one-electron process which is followed by a coupled chemical reaction (EC-mechanism). This mechanism is clearly indicated by the absence of the corresponding reduction peak in the reverse cycle⁶ of the cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 2). The reduction process occurs through the acceptance of two electrons in a single irreversible wave following also the EC-mechanism. The irreversibility of the electrode process is obtained also from the slope of the logarithmic analysis curves⁶ as shown in Table 1. The amino group in compound **2g** can be also oxidised in a first oxidation wave and the nitro group

TABLE 1—DC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a–h AND 3a–h IN BENZONITRILE

Compd. no.	Process	$E_{1/2}$ mV	S^*
2a	OI	1 835	133
	RI	-1 075	114
2b	OI	2 222	66
	RI	-825	99
	RII	-1 203	52
2c	OI	2 002	196
	RI	-1 050	189
2d	OI	2 047	189
	RI	-980	190
2e	OI	2 002	143
	RI	-998	230
2f	OI	1 845	75
	RI	-948	193
2g	OI	748	191
	OII	2 072	178
2h	RI	-972	141
	OI	1 932	130
3a	RI	-1 238	147
	OI	1 932	121
	RI	-723	240
3b	RII	-1 170	199
	OI	2 215	75
	RI	-428	178
3c	RII	-1 088	116
	OI	1 902	84
	RI	-573	215
3d	RII	-1 133	127
	OI	1 912	92
	RI	-583	244
3e	RII	-1 003	88
	OI	1 812	180
	RI	-473	176
3f	RII	-965	62
	OI	1 532	106
	RI	-488	181
3g	RII	-1 043	123
	OI	760	183
	OII	2 030	100
3h	RI	-505	180
	RII	-1 112	130
	OI	1 902	97
	RI	-1 148	178

* $S = dE/d \log (i_a - i)/i$.

Fig. 1. DC-voltammogram of compounds (---) **2d** and (—) **3a** in benzonitrile.

Fig 2 Cyclic voltammogram of compounds **2d** and **3a** in BN. (a) oxidation and (b) reduction; (···) **2d** and (—) **3a** in benzonitrile: scan rate=100 mV s^{-1} .

in compound **2b** reduced in the well-known reduction wave of nitroaromatic compounds.

Arylhydrazone-3-ketophenylpropionitrile (3a-h): These compounds are oxidised in the same manner as compounds **2a-h** in a single irreversible one-electron transfer process following the EC-mechanism. The reduction process is markedly different; although the total number of electrons participating in the electrode reaction is two electrons per molecule as for compounds **2a-h**, these two electrons appear not as a single wave but as a two successive irreversible one-electron waves. The *N*-methyl derivative (**3h**) behaves similarly as **2h**; the reduction occurs in a single two-electron wave.

The polarographic behaviour of this class of compounds has been investigated by several workers⁷. The compounds are reduced in a four-electron wave in either acidic or basic media accompanied by N-N bond cleavage to the corresponding amines. Although this reduction process has been well-documented⁸ it cannot be generalised to account for

the reduction of other substituted α -arylhydrazononitriles since these compounds are tautomeric with the corresponding azo forms. The contribution of each form would depend on the nature of substituents in the molecule. Several articles suggested the existence of certain arylhydrazononitriles in a charge separated azo form⁹. Recently, the different substituted *N*-methylarylhydrazonomesoxalonitriles have been studied in both aqueous and nonaqueous media¹⁰.

In the present work, based on the results, Scheme 1 is suggested for the electrochemical oxidation of the compounds.

Scheme 1

The electrochemical oxidation (Scheme 1) proceeds through a one-electron transfer forming the radical cation with its canonical forms (A) and (B). Mesomer (A) undergoes a dimerisation process leading to the formation of the di-cation **3** which can be stabilised through its combination with two perchlorate anions from the supporting electrolyte forming salt **4**. Also mesomer (B) may be dimerised with proton removal from the *ortho*-position in the phenyl ring leading to the formation of the neutral dimer **5**.

The difference in electron-withdrawing power of the COOC_2H_5 and CN or COC_6H_5 groups plays a significant role in the mode of the reduction process. The high electron-withdrawing power of the CN or COC_6H_5 groups compared with that of COOC_2H_5 group stabilised the firstly formed radical anion which appeared in a well-defined separate one-electron wave.

The reduced centre in these compounds is the N=C double bond which accepts two electrons to form the corresponding dianion. The formed di-anion would be strong enough base to abstract protons from the solution (from the solvent-moisture or from the supporting electrolyte or even from the solvent itself)¹¹ forming compound **6**. It is clear from the structure of **6** (Scheme 2) that it is unstable especially in air, which can be oxidised with air-oxygen to give the starting substance. This is in full agreement

Scheme 2

with the results obtained from CPE. Thus instead of the final product 6, a quantitative yield of the starting material was isolated.

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